

Designing of a web-based application “The Smart Book Store” that allows online shopping

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Abstract: Designing a web store that work properly and fulfil all the demands of the customers is remained a challenge for developers. The increasing importance of e-commerce lead the word to build online shopping centers. In our project, we developed a web-based application. As per a survey, most consumers of online stores are impulsive and usually decide to stay on a site within the first few seconds. “Website design is like a shop interior. If the shop looks poor or like hundreds of other shops the customer is most likely to skip to the other site. Hence, we have designed the project to provide the user with easy navigation, retrieval of data and necessary feedback as much as possible. Our designed web based “The Smart Book Store” application that provides facilities/options to the public like free home delivery, add to Wishlist, can give feedback about website services and relation/service of Client and User.

Keywords: Designing web-application, Asp.Net language, Visual Studio 2013 as platform

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1. Introduction

The increasing importance of e-commerce is apparent in every field of business by using internet. Our inspirations of this venture are every one of those sites who give books online to their clients like Liberty Books [1] it is a standout amongst other book shops in Pakistan, however there are two issues in the site if client does not discover a book they should go to another store and second issue is they don't deliver the books to client.

Our designed web-application “The Smart Book Store” program allows visitors to online shopping. They may view the contents of their shopping cart at any time and may add or delete items at will. The program automatically calculates the total. This is website which helps customers to do the major part of online shopping by using this site and can be managed by online; the Customer can do the all major transaction in a secured way. Here the customer will feel a virtual shopping by adding the selected product to his cart. To ensure the authentication of the customer, she/he must have to register before proceeding. It provides following standard features of any e-commerce web site. Approximately before

three to five years ago work of shopping was done physically in Pakistan also these days shopping is done by physically, but change is becoming rapidly and converting physically to online. “Smart Book store” is a web-based application that will eliminate this kind of problem. Through this a lot of time will be save. This will facilitate the customers to buy books through internet.

There is need to present an online store that solve the problems faced by buyers when they use other online store/applications;, Online Books stores, usually does not take orders from customers;, In case their desired book is not available on the website, they use to refer to other web;, Also, home delivery feature is not commonly found in such websites;, And we special focus, no every time provide services. Through web-based application, “Smart Book Store”, people will select and purchase books from his / her computer. They will login with their username and password and then select the product and add that to their shopping cart and then order and give address and then select payment method and submit the order.

2. Research Methodology

2.1 Scope of Project

Online Book store is available 24 hours a day, and many consumers have Internet access both at work and at home. Searching or browsing an online catalog can be faster than browsing the aisles of a physical store. One can avoid crowded malls resulting in long lines, and no parking some consumers prefer interacting with computers rather than people.

A majority of stores have made it easy to find the style one is looking for, as well as the price range that is acceptable making the shopping experience quick and efficient. The internet has made online an almost effortless task.

2.1.2 Related Projects/Existing Systems

We had been looking forward on many other projects while we were doing our project of online bookstore there were many related projects that we impressed from and inspired. One of related project was Reference: Liberty Books [4]. At this websites user can shop online but can not give his/her feedback. Another thing is that, user can not request which he/she not find at any store.

2.1.3 Software Development Model

Fig. 1: Agile model for developing web-based application

We use “Agile Model “for developing our web-based application as shown in figure 1. This is iterative, time boxed and incremental. This model gives he improved quality of applications.

Agile Model is mostly used because this model provides easy maintenance to the developer. Developer can fix error at every step of developing a software. Incremental and Iterative is the most important features of this model. That’s why we choose this model to develop our web-based application.

2.2 Feature Comparison/Drawbacks in existing system

Table 1. Feature Comparison/Drawbacks in existing system

Sr No.	Comparison Feature	Liberty Books [5]	Fabingo [6]	Global Books [7]	Remarks
1	Home Delivery System. (free)	This Website covers this feature comprehensively.	This Website Covers Home delivery with some charges.	Home delivery available but no order tracking.	Our website completely owns this feature with order tracking, free of charges.
2	Unique Search	Extraordinary Search Feature.	Lacks Author Name Search requests.	Lacks simple keywords issues and author names.	Perfect Algorithm implemented already for this feature in our Website.

Liberty Books [5]

This Website covers this feature comprehensively.

Extraordinary Search Feature.

Fabingo [6]

This Website Covers Home delivery with some charges.

Lacks Author Name Search requests.

Global Books [7]

Home delivery available but no order tracking.

Lacks simple keywords issues and author names.

Our Web site complete with features like searching Books by tittle, by Author, User can pay cash on delivery, no delivery charges, Users can give their feedbacks

3.1 Requirements

3.1.1 Functional Requirements:

Table 2. Functional Requirements

Reference no:	Methods	Categories	Attributes	Details
R1	New Users Fill the Sign-up Form.	Functional	Sign Up	Information about user, save to data base. Provide legal information like First Name, Last Name, username, password, Address, city, Phone Number
R2	User Should Log In First.	Functional	Log in	Provide correct Information Email Address Password

R2.1	Generate error message.	Functional	Message generation	Generate error message if provided information is incorrect
R3	Add to cart	Functional	Add book	For book selection User must add book into his cart
R3.1	Delete to cart	Functional	Delete book	User can delete his book from his cart
R4	Search book	Evident	Search book	If user does not find book he can search book from our database
R5	User request	Functional	request	If some case user will not find book from our database user can request us to add this book on his request .

3.1.2 System Attributes/ Non-functional Requirements

Table 3 System Attributes/ Non-functional Requirements

<i>Attribute</i>	<i>Details and Boundary Constraints</i>	<i>Category</i>
Response moment	User search Result will appear within 25 seconds	Optional
Easy search	Easy to search by giving drop down menu	Mandatory
Privacy	Hide the personal information only available if user wants to share it	Mandatory
User Load	A minimum of 100 users connected at a same time	Mandatory
Availability	Required User Must Be Online.	Optional
Usability	Interface must be efficient	Optional
Access Efficiency	Easy to access the required person.	Mandatory
Security	User credentials Must be secure	Mandatory
User Friendly	App should be user friendly and easy to understand (how to use?)	Mandatory
Consistency	App should have stability	Mandatory
Reliability	App should be reliable	Mandatory

3.2 Tools Selection

3.2.1 Hardware Requirements

Processor: core i3 or above **RAM** : 1 GB or above **Hard disk:** 40 GB or above

3.2.2 Software Requirements

Operating System: - Windows 10, Windows 8.1, **Front-end tool:** - ASP.NET, Visual Studio 2013 **Back-end:** - MSSQL 2012

3.3.1 ERD

relations

Fig. 2

ERD

Fig. 3.

3.3.2 User Use Cases

Use case Diagram of User and Admin

Fig. 4

3.3.3 Class Diagram

Each customer has unique id and is linked to exactly one **account**. Account owns shopping cart and orders. Customer could register as a web user to be able to buy items online

Fig. 5. Class diagram

3.3.4 Sequence Diagrams

Sequence Diagrams Represent the objects participating the interaction horizontally and time vertically.

Admin Sequence Diagram

Fig. 6. Sign Up, Sequence Diagram, Signup setup

Fig. 7. Manage Book, Delete Book, Sequence Diagram Delete Book Admin setup diagram

Fig. 8. Add Book Sequence Diagram Add Book Admin setup diagram

Fig. 9. Order Status Sequence Diagram Order Status Admin setup diagram

Fig. 10. User Sequence Diagrams, Sign Up, Sequence Diagram Sign Up User setup diagram

Fig. 11. Request Book, Sequence Diagram Request Book User Add to Cart setup diagram

Fig. 12. Sequence Diagram Add to Cart User setup diagram

Fig. 13. Order Status, Sequence Diagram Order Status User setup diagram

Fig. 14. Sign In Sequence Diagram Sign in Admin/User setup diagram

Fig. 15. Search Book, Sequence Diagram

3.4 Database Model (Database Diagram)

Database Model, Back End Database Tables

Tables:

Contact Table:

It has contact related data and contact id is primary key.

Add to Cart Table:

It has added to cart information related data and cart id is primary key this will has user id image path cost and quality and credit card information.

Add To Cart Table

Table 4. Add To Cart Table

Column Name	Data Type	Allow Nulls
CID	int	<input type="checkbox"/>
PID	int	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Name	varchar(50)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Image	varchar(500)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Price	varchar(50)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Quantity	varchar(50)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Total	varchar(50)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
		<input type="checkbox"/>

Products Table:

This table has the products this has a name quality and pid.

Table 5 Products Table:

Column Name	Data Type	Allow Nulls
id	int	<input type="checkbox"/>
Title	varchar(50)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Author	varchar(50)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Field	varchar(50)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Subject	varchar(50)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Edition	varchar(50)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Pages	varchar(50)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
YOP	varchar(50)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Price	decimal(18, 0)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Stock	varchar(50)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Status	varchar(500)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
TableOfContent	varchar(500)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Image	varchar(500)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Employee Table

Table 6 Employee Table

Column Name	Data Type	Allow Nulls
id	int	<input type="checkbox"/>
CNIC	varchar(200)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Name	varchar(200)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
FatherName	varchar(200)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Contact	varchar(200)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Email	varchar(200)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
City	varchar(200)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Address	varchar(200)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Salary	varchar(200)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Designation	varchar(200)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
JoiningDate	date	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
UserName	varchar(200)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Password	varchar(200)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Implementation & User Interface

4.1 DEVELOPMENT SETUP

Creately :

This tool majorly helps us with our Diagrams which were required in Documentation phase. This tool was very helpful in creating diagrams and flow charts and different tables. Easily draw diagrams online using Creately's online diagramming tool. Diagram software packed with templates and features.

Sublime Text :

We use this tool for coding purpose. Primarily we use this tool for HTML work and CSS work. We did our entire code on Sublime Text 3 Build 3103.

MSSQL :

For our Database, we use MSSQL tool. MSSQL was used as a back end database since it is one of the most open source database, and it provide fast data access, easy installation and simplicity.

Xampp :

We use this tool on start of our project. This tool helps us in making localhost server through Apache server. Xampp is most powerful for PHP development Environment.

4.1.2 Deployment setup

We deployed our project on GODaddy server, we did our manual configuration on htaccess file, and we deploy our database on same server.

4.1.3 Algorithms

When user Add any book to his/her cart, and go for checkout there will be algorithm of FIFO, first in first out. We will serve customers based on FIFO method, we will deliver books on the basis of algorithm like if someone came first and made checkout we will put him in queue and set his priority.

Constraint and Restrictions

- System will allow a user to buy ten books only at one time.
- Password reset will be allowed to only those who have valid code.
- Log in OR Sign Up is must for any user to check out the book.
- Location must be Lahore, otherwise no Delivery will be entertained.
- Password should be 8 letters and no case sensitive.

Limitations

Our website is only can be accessed from browsers.

There will be copyrights limitation because we outsourcing our purchases too.

4.2.3 User interface

Home page

Figure 16. User interface home page

User Register

REGISTER YOURSELF HERE

Name

Father Name

CNIC

Contact No

Email

City

Address

UserName

Password

UPload Your Image No file chosen

Figure 2. User registration interface

Admin

SMART BOOK STORE

HOME CATEGORY BOOKS EMPLOYEE CUSTOMERS ORDERS WISHLIST FEEDBACK LOGOUT

OrderID	CustomerID	Amount
Delete4	1	7400
Delete3	1	1400
Delete2	1	6000
Delete1	1	2000

Figure 18. Admin home page interface

4.3 Source Codes

User login:

```

asp:Content ID="Content1" ContentPlaceHolderID="ContentPlaceHolder1" Runat="Server">
<table style="width: 100%">
  <tr>
    <td colspan="2" style="text-align: center; font-size: x-large; color: #6C0000">UserLogin</td>
  </tr>
  <tr>
    <td style="width: 473px; height: 40px;" class="text-right">UserName:</td>
    <td style="height: 40px" class="text-left">
      <asp:TextBox ID="TextBox1" runat="server"></asp:TextBox>
    </td>
  </tr>
  <tr>
    <td style="width: 473px;" class="text-right">Password:</td>
    <td class="text-left">
      <asp:TextBox ID="TextBox2" runat="server" TextMode="Password"></asp:TextBox>
    </td>
  </tr>
  <tr>
    <td style="width: 473px" class="text-right">
      <asp:LinkButton ID="LinkButton1" runat="server" OnClick="LinkButton1_Click" PostBackUrl="~/Register.aspx">New User? Get Registered</asp>
    </td>
    <td class="text-left">
      <asp:Button ID="Button1" runat="server" OnClick="Button1_Click" Text="Login" Width="131px" />
      <asp:Label ID="lblmsg" runat="server"></asp:Label>
    </td>
  </tr>
</table>

```

Admin Login:

```

<asp:Content ID="Content1" ContentPlaceHolderID="ContentPlaceHolder1" Runat="Server">
  <table style="width: 100%">
    <tr>
      <td colspan="3" style="text-align: center; font-size: x-large; color: #6C0000">AdminLogin</td>
    </tr>
    <tr>
      <td style="text-align: right; width: 556px;">UserName:</td>
      <td class="text-left">
        <asp:TextBox ID="TextBox1" runat="server"></asp:TextBox>
      </td>
    </tr>
    <tr>
      <td style="text-align: right; width: 556px; height: 25px;">Password:</td>
      <td style="height: 25px" class="text-left">
        <asp:TextBox ID="TextBox2" runat="server" TextMode="Password"></asp:TextBox>
      </td>
    </tr>
  </table>
  <td style="width: 556px;">

```

Home Page:

```

</div>
</div>
<div class="navbar-collapse collapse">
  <div class="menu">
    <ul class="nav nav-tabs" role="tablist">
      <li class="current_page_item"><a href="Home.aspx" accesskey="1" title="">Home</a></li>
      <li><a href="Books.aspx" accesskey="1" title="">Books Gallery</a></li>
      <li><a href="UserLogin.aspx" accesskey="3" title="">User Login</a></li>
      <li><a href="FeedBack.aspx" accesskey="4" title="">FeedBack</a></li>
      <li><a href="Contact.aspx" accesskey="4" title="">Contact us</a></li>
    </ul>
  </div>
</div>
</div>
</nav>
</header>
<!-- Start WOWSlider.com BODY section --> <!-- add to the <body> of your page -->
<div id="wowslider-container1">
<div class="ws_images"><ul>
<li></li>
<li></li>
<li></li>

```

Manage Books:

```

<br />
<asp:GridView ID="GridView1" runat="server" AutoGenerateColumns="False" CellPadding="4" DataKeyNames="id" DataSourceID="SqlDataSource1" Em
  <AlternatingRowStyle BackColor="White" />
  <Columns>
    <asp:CommandField ShowDeleteButton="True" ShowEditButton="True" />
    <asp:BoundField DataField="id" HeaderText="id" ReadOnly="True" SortExpression="id" />
    <asp:BoundField DataField="Category" HeaderText="Category" SortExpression="Category" />
    <asp:BoundField DataField="Title" HeaderText="Title" SortExpression="Title" />
    <asp:BoundField DataField="Author" HeaderText="Author" SortExpression="Author" />
    <asp:BoundField DataField="Field" HeaderText="Field" SortExpression="Field" />
    <asp:BoundField DataField="Subject" HeaderText="Subject" SortExpression="Subject" />
    <asp:BoundField DataField="Edition" HeaderText="Edition" SortExpression="Edition" />
    <asp:BoundField DataField="Pages" HeaderText="Pages" SortExpression="Pages" />
    <asp:BoundField DataField="YOP" HeaderText="YOP" SortExpression="YOP" />
    <asp:BoundField DataField="Price" HeaderText="Price" SortExpression="Price" />
    <asp:BoundField DataField="Stock" HeaderText="Stock" SortExpression="Stock" />
    <asp:BoundField DataField="Status" HeaderText="Status" SortExpression="Status" />
    <asp:BoundField DataField="TableOfContent" HeaderText="TableOfContent" SortExpression="TableOfContent" />
    <asp:BoundField DataField="Image" HeaderText="Image" SortExpression="Image" />
    <asp:BoundField DataField="Date" HeaderText="Date" SortExpression="Date" />
    <asp:ImageField DataImageUrlField="Image" DataImageUrlFormatString="~/Books/{0}" ControlStyle-Width="120" ControlStyle-Height="120
  </asp:ImageField>
  </Columns>
  <FooterStyle BackColor="#990000" Font-Bold="True" ForeColor="White" />
  <HeaderStyle BackColor="#990000" Font-Bold="True" ForeColor="White" />
  <PagerStyle BackColor="#FFCC66" ForeColor="#333333" HorizontalAlign="Center" />

```

4.4 Results

The results are given below.

- It provides facilities to the public with home delivery
- We provide free home delivery.
- We provide Wishlist to fulfill the needs of clients.
- User can give feedback about website services.
- Client will be satisfied with our services.
- Relation will be created between Client and User.

5. Conclusion

The Internet has become a major resource in modern business. As per a survey, most consumers of online stores are impulsive and usually make a decision to stay on a site within the first few seconds. "Website design is like a shop interior. If the shop looks poor or like hundreds of other shops the customer is most likely to skip to the other site. Hence we have designed the project to provide the user with easy navigation, retrieval of data and necessary feedback as much as possible.

In this project, the user is provided with an e-commerce web site that can be used to buy books online. MSSQL was used as back-end database since it is one of the most popular open source databases, and it provides fast data access, easy installation and simplicity. A good shopping cart design must be accompanied with user-friendly shopping cart application logic. It should be convenient for the customer to view the contents of their cart and to be able to remove or add items to their cart.

The shopping cart application described in this project provides a number of features that are designed to make the customer more comfortable. This project helps in understanding the creation of an interactive web page and the technologies used to implement it. The design of the project which includes Data Model and Process Model illustrates how the database is built with different tables, how the data is accessed and processed from the tables.

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- [10] www.aspfree.com
- [11] www.4guysfromrolla.com/index.aspx
- [12] www.support.mircosoft.com
- [13] www.asptoday.com
- [14] www.fmexpense.com/quickstart/aspplus/default.com
- [15] www.developer.com